

The Examination of the Relationship between Perceived Organizational Support, Contextual Performance and Work Engagement: The Role of Transformational Leadership

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Abstract:- The contextual performance of employees in companies is an essential component of performance since volunteer behaviors play a significant role in daily work, there is currently a limited understanding of the voluntary behaviors that organizations take beyond their mandatory task requirements, though these are critical elements for the overall effectiveness of the companies. In this study, the concepts of Perceived Organizational Support, Contextual Performance, Work Engagement, and Transformational Leadership, which are among the important concepts for organizations, are focused on.

The Perceived Organizational Support Scale, Contextual Performance Scale, Work Engagement, and Transformational Leadership Scales were used to collect data for this study. White-collar service industry workers in Turkey make up the study's sample. The SPSS program, a statistical package used for social science research, was used to evaluate the data collected from the questionnaire given to a total of 384 participants. This study's major goal is to evaluate how organizational support affects contextual performance and how transformational leadership functions in this environment. In terms of employee engagement and work performance, the study project's goal is to look at how organizational support on a general level impacts contextual performance in organizations. also, describe the part that leadership plays in this relationship.

The associations between the variables were clarified as a result of the regression and moderator analyses. Findings have proven that perceived Organizations Support (POS) has a 31% positive effect on the contextual Performance of employees in white-collar employees in the servant sector in Turkey ($B=310$, $P=000$, $F=40.709$). It was found that perceived Organizations Support (POS) has a 27.4% effect on the work engagement of employees in white-collar employees in the servant sector in Turkey ($B=.274$, $P=000$, $F, 30.919$). Thirdly, it was found that transformational leadership was a significant indicator of Perceived Organizational Support and Contextual performance of employees with ($t=5.636$, $P= 0.000$, $R=.361$, $R^2 =.130$, $F= 28.52$, $P= 0.000$) and finally transformational leadership was a significant indicator of Perceived Organizational Support and work engagement of employees with ($B=.660$, $P= 0.000$).The research comes to two conclusions: first, that perceived organizational support has had a minor impact on

contextual performance, the effect being positive; and secondly, the study concludes that perceived organizational support is significant in inducing the work engagement amongst the employees.

Keywords:- Perceived organizational support, contextual performance, transformational leadership, work engagement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The business environment's constant change and the pace at which it occurs are the main characteristics of today's modern business world. As a result, businesses are engaged in intense competition to establish a competitive edge and accelerate innovation and technological advancement (Cho, J., & Dansereau, F., 2010). The official CEO of GM also stated that any business that wants to succeed in the severe competition must work to engage its own workforce. It has been demonstrated that workers' work engagement and contextual performance have a significant favorable impact on the advantages and long-term growth of the organization.(Manesh, M. H., Singh, J. S. K., & Hussain, I. A. B., 2016).

Perceived organizational support (POS), which employees view as the organization's commitment to their contribution, well-being, development, and identity, is another element determining overall contextual performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. (Arvey, R. D., & Murphy, K. R., 1998). Contextual performance broadens the notion of performance to encompass a variety of non-job-specific behaviors. It refers to work activities that may not immediately contribute to the technological core of the business but are nevertheless advantageous, such as volunteering and assisting others. Contextual activities are said to have an effect on and support the psychological and social environment of the organization. Transformational leadership is a topic that researchers in this field are particularly interested in. Transformational leadership encourages both improved employee productivity and organizational effectiveness.(Almatrooshi, B., Singh, S. K., & Farouk, S., 2916).

Additionally, a crucial prerequisite for organizational commitment is transformative leadership. It has been demonstrated that transformational leadership can affect decision-making procedures while acknowledging the

importance of involvement, communication, and participation. Transformational leaders encourage their team members to perform at better levels both personally and for the organization by involving them in building an appealing future. Getting their staff members involved and committed to the company ultimately helps them feel fulfilled, responsible, and satisfied with their jobs.(Sinclair, R. R., Tucker, J. S., Cullen, J. C., & Wright, C., 2005).

A. Statement of the Problem

One could argue that businesses no longer view the human aspect as a cost to be borne in order to achieve their objectives of profitability and efficiency. Because modern management is now widely understood, businesses are altering how they approach their workforces and work environments. Companies today confront numerous difficulties when it comes to hiring and human resources. Finding qualified workers and recruiting them to jobs is one of these difficulties. The largest challenge is preparing and keeping on board personnel who will perform additional voluntary work, serve as good corporate citizens, communicate with coworkers and engage in other volunteer activities, and foster the finest organizational culture possible. Numerous scholars have studied these topics, but not to the extent that we do now regarding the significance of these problems, notably contextual performance and perceived organizational support. Therefore, the aim is to investigate the relationship between work engagement and context in companies and how they are impacted, as well as how organizational support influences contextual performance and work engagement. As a result, this study advances knowledge of the relationship between contextual performance and perceived organizational support, which is considered to be crucial for organizations in the modern day, and the function of transformational leadership in that relationship.

D. Conceptual Framework

B. Research Hypothesis

- Hypothesis 1 (H1): Employees' contextual performance is significantly and favorably impacted by their perception of organizational support.
- Hypothesis 2 (H2): Perceived organizational support significantly and favorably affects workers' work engagement.
- Additional Hypothesis (H3): Transformational leadership can moderate the relationship between employees' perceptions of organizational support and their performance in specific contexts.
- Additional Hypothesis (H4): Transformational leadership plays a moderating impact in the relationship between employees' perceptions of organizational support and their level of work engagement.

C. Importance of the Study

Contextual performance in businesses is now extremely significant and crucial because of the fierce competition among businesses, the development of contemporary technology, and their involvement in daily performance. Employees are now expected to perform better than their job descriptions and daily performance. Contextual performance is significant because it exemplifies a behavior type that is substantially controlled by an individual's motive. Few studies have addressed how the ability to engage in contextual behaviors can be constrained by situational demands. Previous research has shown that sustained employee performance is positively influenced by transformational leadership. Contextual performance (CP), which complements individual task performance and improves organizational performance, is the outcome of this extra effort or pro-social conduct.

Fig. 1: Hypothesis Conceptual Model

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for the study is provided in this chapter, and the chapter's primary goal is to gather pertinent data on the issue, which is a difficult task. This section frequently covers subjects like looking at the research's conceptual framework, reviewing pertinent literature, research background, theoretical framework, etc.

A. The Concept of Contextual Performance

Performance is the degree to which actions accomplish the desired outcome. (Akal, 1992). Performance is, in other words, the "rate of purpose fulfillment" or the "degree of activity output." This level denotes the degree to which the intention or objective has been accomplished. Depending on their point of view, various institutions have varied definitions of performance. The performance of the institution and the person are used to define the degree of achievement. Some academics, like Campbell, contend that performance includes both the deed and its outcome. Performance, according to Campbell, is defined as conduct that is acceptable to the organization's aim and that can be assessed based on amount of contribution.(Suliman, 2001).

B. Task Performance and Contextual Performance: A Comparison

According to John Hunthausen, there are two main groups for the various theories' components. (Hunthausen, 2000)(1) completing individual tasks; and (2) taking steps to establish and maintain the social and organizational structure required for others to do their assigned responsibilities.

The following three underlying presumptions aid in separating task- and context-specific performance: Third, contextual performance is optional and outside of the job, but task performance is required and consists of conduct within the position. Contextual performance is tied to personality and motivation, whereas task performance is related to skills. First of all, unlike task performance, which varies across tasks, contextual performance is constant across jobs.(Peter Hosie, Alan Nankervis, 2016).

Motowidlo et al. (1997) make a distinction between contextual performance and task performance, as shown in the picture below. Motowidlo et al. (1997) divided performance into task and environmental categories to identify performance-related factors. According to Motowidlo et al., task performance was associated to cognitive capacity whereas contextual performance was related to personality. Motowidlo and Van Scotter in 1994 confirmed the findings of MacKenzie et al. (1991) that contextual and task performance are influenced by a variety of factors. Knowledge, skills, and work habits have an effect on personality and cognitive performance, claim Motowidlo et al. (1997).(Motowidlo, S.J., Borman, W.C. and Schmit, M.J, 1997).

Fig. 2: Task Performance Vs Contextual Performance (Source: Motowidlo et al. (1997)

While contextual performance is stable across the majority of jobs, task performance varies and vary by employment. Task performance is the effectiveness with which tasks are accomplished. Therefore, contextual performance "has the effect of maintaining the broader organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function," whereas it makes

sense to attribute variances in tasks performed as well as individual knowledge, skills, and aptitude to task performance variability among employees.(Motowidlo, S.J., Borman, W.C. and Schmit, M.J, 1997).

C. Analysis and Measuring of Performance

The authors of Hasan Tutar and et al. (2011) note that there are two techniques to assess performance. Task performance is the first, while contextual performance is the second. Task performance is the work responsibility that directly applies technical processes, delivers necessary goods or services, or somehow combines tasks that contribute to the technical foundation of the organization. (Borman, W. C., & Motowidlo, S. J., 1997). Task performance is concentrated on a task's essential technical components. Contextual performance includes psychological performance circumstances such as voluntariness, optional activities, attendance, and motivation. (Van Scotter JR, & Motowidlo SJ., 1996). Task and contextual performance are also included in the institutional outcomes. Employees must understand the goal and get motivated to achieve it. They also need to be given directing resources, such as authorization and empowerment. (Hasan Tutar, Mehmet Altinoz, & Demet Cakiroglu, 2011).

D. The Relationship between Work Engagement and Performance

The business must value and foster employee involvement, which involves both the employer and the employee. (Robinson, D., Perryman, S., & Hayday, S., 2004). A positive attitude toward the organization and its standards is what we call employee engagement. Ncube and Jerie (2012) claim that attention and absorption are the two components of the psychological state of involvement. While absorption refers to becoming fully involved in a role and describes the intensity of one's concentration on a part, attentiveness relates to mental preparation and the amount of time spent thinking about a role. (Gebauer, J., Lowman, D., & Gordon, J., 2008; Hazrat Bilal, Bahadar Shah, Muhammad Yasir & Abdul Mateen, 2015).

According to Babcock-Roberson and Strickland, there is a connection between employee engagement and contextual performance (2010). They found a strong positive correlation between worker involvement and performance in the context. (Babcock-Roberson, M. E., & Strickland, O. J., 2010).

E. The Concept of Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

As per organizational support theory, employees' tendency to attribute human qualities to the business promotes the growth of POS. (Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D., 1986). Levinson stated that actions made by organization agents are frequently seen as indicative of the organization's goal rather than being entirely attributable to an individual's objectives. Levinson contends that this personification of the organization is a result of the organization's legal, ethical, and financial responsibility for the actions of its agents; organizational policies, norms, and culture that maintain continuity and define acceptable behaviors; and the power the organization's agents have over particular employees. (Levinson, 1965). Depending on how the organization is portrayed, employees may view favorable or

unfavorable treatment as a sign that the company likes or dislikes them.

F. Antecedents of Perceived Organizational Support

According to organizational support theory (Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D., 1986), Fairness, supervisor support, organizational awards, and favorable job circumstances are three ways that the organization is regarded to treat its employees favorably, and they should all increase POS. Commonly omit the phrase perceived while addressing the perceptions of positive treatment that result in POS in order to reduce repetition. A few studies examined the association between personality and POS, even though the majority of studies examined the relationship between employees' views of positive treatment and POS.

G. The Implications of Perceived Organizational Support

The research findings of Rhoades and Eisenberger show that POS deployment in the companies has a wide range of effects. These effects might include organizational commitment, job-related affect, job involvement, performance, strains, desire to stay, and withdrawal behavior. POS should instill a sense of duty to care about the organization's well-being based on the reciprocity principle and organizational commitment. The urge to exchange care for caring should build employees' emotional ties to the personified organization. (Foa, E. B., & Foa, U. G., 1980). By fulfilling socioemotional needs like affiliation and emotional support, one can strengthen affective commitment. (Armeli, S., Eisenberger, R., Fasolo, P., & Lynch, P., 1998).

Job involvement is defined as identification with and interest in the particular work one performs on the job. (Cropanzano, R., Howes, J. C., Grandey, A. A., & Toth, P., 1997; O'Driscoll, M. P., & Randall, D. M., 1999). It has been found that task interest and perceived skill are related. POS could boost workers' commitment to their jobs by elevating their perceived knowledge. (Linda Rhoades and Robert Eisenberger, 2002).

H. The Concept of Leadership and Transformational leadership

a) Transformational Leadership

Businesses are putting more focus on acquiring the proper leadership traits in order to handle intense competitive pressure and manage a complicated and unpredictable environment. According to studies, transformational leadership is especially good at boosting organizational performance in uncertain environments and fostering competition, both of which are beneficial to businesses. (Nemanich, L., & Keller, R., 2007). James MacGregor Burns first introduced the idea of transformative leadership in 1978. In order to achieve higher levels of motivation and morale, Burns defines transformational leadership as a method that "leaders and followers support one another in attaining."

Transformational leaders are those who have a positive outlook on the future of their organizations, prioritize strengthening employees' self-confidence by helping them reach their potential, share with staff an achievable mission and vision for the company, and work together with staff to identify and address needs. (Peterson, S. J., Walumbwa, F. O., Byron, K., & Myrowitz, J., 2008).

Along with using human resource management and organizational learning techniques, transformational leaders put special emphasis on creating a culture that supports knowledge. There are two types of knowledge: explicit knowledge, which is transferable, simple to manage, documentable, and storable; and tacit knowledge, which is specific, valuable, underutilized, unarticulated, and resides in employees' heads. (John Kissi, Andrew Dainty, Martin Tuuli, 2013).

III. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The three basic types of analysis used in social sciences and economics research are qualitative, quantitative, and mixed. A scientific method for learning more about people and the humanities and understanding how people perceive the world is qualitative research. On the other hand, quantitative analysis is a form of analysis that generates numerical data and persuasive evidence using mathematical techniques and statistical analysis. Only within a different time period than that of the longitudinal study can data be collected for a cross-sectional survey, therefore that is what the researcher did. In this study, a self-administered questionnaire was utilized to collect data using both quantitative and logical methods to determine the link between variables. The association between variables must be explained by explanatory research, therefore statistical tests like reliability and demographics were clearly explained utilizing the quantitative technique. (Creswell, 2003).

The quantitative research approach helps us to test the objective theories by documenting the relationship between the variables. The pertinent study is created using the quantitative research methodology. The four different scale questions were combined while taking into account the correlations between the elements. Online surveys were used to collect numerical data. a method of data collecting used alone. Because of the qualities of the research scales and the study's hypotheses, a cross-sectional technique was used. The questionnaires, which included perceived organizational support, contextual performance, transformational leadership, and job engagement as independent, dependent, and moderating variables, received responses from workers in Turkey's service sector. After gathering the data, it was analyzed using the SPSS program, and the results were shown in the relevant tables. The

researchers can use online questionnaires to obtain the scales' numerical results.

B. Population and Sample Size

White collar workers in Istanbul, Turkey's service industry make up the study's sample. The survey of this study, which was conducted among 385 employees of various organizations in Istanbul, Turkey, who work in the service industry, was disseminated as a questionnaire.

C. Questionnaire Design

The primary data collection method for this study has been modified to use questionnaires. The questionnaire is used to record respondents' impressions and opinions as well as to categorize, compare, or display respondents' beliefs, feelings, desires, wishes, and behaviors as individuals and as a community. (Bell, E., & Bryman, A., 2007). An online survey is used to gather information from a random sample of white-collar workers in the service industry. At the conclusion of the procedure, 385 valid answers are gathered. The survey consists of 43 questions. 8 items on the Contextual Performance Scale created by Van Dyne (ARYEE, S., SUN, L. Y., & ZHOU, Q., 2009); 10 items on the Transformational Leadership Scale and 17 items on the Work Engagement Scale (Booth-Butterfield, S., & Booth-Butterfield, M., 1991); 8 items on the Scale of Perceived Organizational Support (Rhoades, L., & Eisenberger, R., 2002). Each comment is given a Likert scale rating out of five (1 being strongly disagreed with and 5 being strongly agreed with).

D. Frequency of Socio Demographic

A study looked at white-collar workers in Turkey's service sector. Male respondents made up 59.4% of the population, while female respondents made up the remaining 40.6%. 43 percent of the respondents, it was discovered, were between the ages of 18 and 25. 53.4 percent of respondents, or the bulk of the population, were between the ages of 26 and 35. The population's median age was between 36 and 45, making up 3.6% of the total. Regarding education, 54.4% of respondents had a master's degree, compared to 44.8 percent of persons with a bachelor's degree. 1.8 percent of the respondents had a PhD. When it came to frequency, the participants with 2 to 5 years of experience in the service industry received the most arrivals at this query (71.4 percent of the sample size). Less than a year of work experience was had by 13.8 percent of participants. While 3.6 percent of participants had more than eleven years of job experience, 11.2 percent of participants had between six and ten years. 58.9% of participants had less than a year of experience working for their present firms, according to a final study of job experience. The data for the poll came from a total of 384 respondents, of whom 36.5 percent had between 2 and 5 years of work experience and 4.8 percent had more than 6 years.

Variable		Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	228	59.4
	Female	156	40.6
	Total	384	100.0
Age	18-25	165	43.0
	26-35	205	53.4
	36-45	14	3.6
	Total	384	100.0
Education	Bachelor	172	44.8
	Master	205	53.4
	PhD	7	1.8
	Total	384	100.0
Work Experiences in Service Sector	0-1 year	53	13.8
	2-5 years	274	71.4
	6-10 years	43	11.2
	+11 years	14	3.6
	Total	384	100.0
Work experience in current Company	0-1 year	226	58.9
	2-5 years	140	36.5
	+6 years	18	4.7
	Total	384	100.0

Table 1: Frequency of Socio Demographic

Source: Data, 2022

IV. FACTOR AND RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE SCALES

To establish the factor composition of the scales employed in the study, a confirmatory factor analysis and reliability tests were first carried out. Perceived Organizational Support (POS), Contextual Performance (CP), Work Engagement (16 questions in the study), and Transformational Leadership (11) are among the scales on which the variables are composed. Before moving on to test the hypotheses, the study determined that it was important to determine the validity and reliability of the scales. It is crucial to assess the Cronbach's alpha concept and the Kaiser Meyer-Okin (KMO) sampling measure for the validity of the scales employed in this study. The results show that the KMO value scales are at least 0.827, that the KMO value exceeds the KMO value typically used in statistics (the suggested KMO value of at least .600), and that the Bartlett's test of sphericity of each scale is significant based on the study (p-value = .000). Because the factor loadings are less than 0.50, only the statement "When there is no manager or other group members in the institution, I follow the orders even in moments" has a loading of .473. I am also highly insistent about overcoming hurdles to finish

the task. I make a stand in 489 that is appropriate for my place of employment to represent my place of employment outside of work. I give a compelling picture of what we are capable of doing with 472. From the scale, 466 were disqualified. Four elements were disregarded because their factor loads were less than 0.5.

A. Regression Analysis Findings

The results of the factor and reliability analyses showed how this study was used to evaluate the validity and reliability of the scale constructs and to test the study's premise. The basic hypothesis could be tested further using regression analysis. These are the research's hypotheses: The first hypothesis (H1) states that perceptions of organizational support have a considerable and favourable impact on employees' contextual performance. Hypothesis 2 (H2): Employee engagement at work is considerably and favorably influenced by perceived organizational support. The third hypothesis (H3) states that transformational leadership can affect how people perceive organizational support and how well they perform in particular situations. and H4: The association between employees' views of organizational support and their level of work engagement is moderated by transformational leadership.

• **Hypothesis 1 (H1):Employees' contextual performance is significantly and favorably impacted by their perception of organizational support.**

Variable	β	Std. Error	t	P
(Constant)	2.454	.148	16.525	.000***
Perceived Organization Support	.293	.046	6.380	.000***

R= .310^a; F= 40.709; P<.000
 a. *p<0,05; **p<0.00*** p<.000
 b. Dependent Variable: Contextual Performance (CP)
 c. independent variable: Perceived Organizations Support (POS)

Table 2: Effect of perceived Organizational Support on Contextual Performance of employees

Source: Data, 2022

The results of Table 2 show that perceived organizational support (POS) has a moderate influence on the contextual performance of Turkish service sector employees who are white (R=.310^a, P=.000, F, 40.709). This influence is proven to have a 31 percent impact on these employees' contextual performance. The results demonstrate

that Turkish service employees of white hue perform marginally better in context when perceived organizational support is increased. The data corroborate the hypothesis's assertion that "Employees' contextual performance is greatly and favorably impacted by their perception of organizational support."

• **Hypothesis 2 (H2):Perceived organizational support significantly and favorably affects workers' work engagement.**

Variable	β	Std. Error	t	P
(Constant)	2.523	.175	14.427	.000***
Perceived Organization support	.300	.054	5.561	.000***

R= .274; F= 30.919; P<.000
 a. *p<0,05; **p<0.00*** p<.000
 b. Dependent Variable: Work engagement of employees (WEO)
 c. independent variable: Perceived Organizational Support

Table 3: Effect of Employee Work Engagement and Perceived Organizational Support

Source: Data, 2022

According to Table 3's findings, perceived organizational support (POS) only has a 27.4 percent impact on workers' work engagement who are white and employed in the service sector in Turkey (R=.274, P=.000, F, 30.919). This suggests that perceived organizational support has little

bearing on workers' work engagement. According to the findings, raising the perceived level of organizational support enhances the work engagement of Turkish employees of white color working in the service industry.

• **Hypothesis 3 (H3):Transformational leadership can moderate the relationship between employees' perceptions of organizational support and their performance in specific contexts.**

Variable	β	Std. Error	t	P
(Constant)	2.015	.185	10.890	.000
Perceived Organization Support	.259	.046	5.636	.000
Transformational Leadership	.164	.042	3.856	.000

Perceived Organization Support	Transformational Leadership	Moderator effect β	SE	t	P
Moderator Effect of Transformational leadership= M+1SD					
M-1SS (2.512) Low		2.651	0.211	3.135	0.000
M(3.512) Moderate		3.121	0.310	7.132	0.000
M+1SS(4+121 High		4.156	0.412	8.104	0.000
Model Summary	R	R²	F	P	
		R ² Change	F	df1	df2
	.034	28.52	1.000	.381	0.000

Table 4: Analysis of transformational leadership's influence on the connection between employees' perceived organizational support and context-specific performance

Source: Data, 2022

According to table 4's findings (t=5.636, P=0.000, R=.361, R2 =.130, F= 28.52, P=0.000), transformational leadership was a strong predictor of employees' perceptions of organizational support and contextual performance. According to the study's findings, there is a weak correlation between white employees' performance in the context of their perceived organizational support and transformation leadership in Turkey's service sector. The findings indicate that there is only a weak correlation between employees' perceived organizational support and their contextual performance. Thus, the relationship between

the POS and contextual performance must be moderated by transformation leadership.

• **Hypothesis4 (H4):Transformational leadership plays a moderating impact in the relationship between employees' perceptions of organizational support and their level of work engagement.**

The fourth hypothesis examined the moderating effect of transformational leadership on the association between perceived organizational support and employee work engagement. The results are presented in Table 5.

Variable	β	Std. Error	t	P
(Constant) WE	.857	.173	4.939	.000
Perceived Organisation Support	.172	.043	3.988	.000
Transformational Leadership	.621	.040	15.622	.000

Perceived Organization Support	Transformational Leadership	Moderator effect β	SE	t	P
Moderator Effect of Transformational leadership= M+1SD					
M- 1SS (2.901) Low		3.010	0.312	4.123	0.000
M(3.981) Moderate		4.123	0.412	8.213	0.000
M+1SS(5+11 High		5.421	0.512	9.431	0.000
Model Summary	R	R²	F	P	
	.660	.436	147.3	0.000	
		R ² Change	F	df1	df2
	.361	244.06	1.000	.381	0.000

Table 5: Analysis of transformational leadership moderated by perceptions of organizational support and employee work engagement (WE)

Source: Data, 2022

Table 5's findings show that transformational leadership was a strong predictor of employee job engagement and perceived organizational support ($t=3.988$, $P=0.000$, $R=.660$, $R^2=.436$, $F=244.06$). According to the study's findings, there is a weak correlation between white employees' performance in the context of their perceived organizational support and transformation leadership in Turkey's service sector. The findings indicate that there is only a weak correlation between employees' perceived organizational support and their contextual performance. Thus, the relationship between the POS and contextual performance must be moderated by transformation leadership.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

a) Hypothesis 1 (H1): Employees' contextual performance is significantly and favorably impacted by their perception of organizational support.

According to a study conducted in Turkey, perceived organizational support (POS) has a moderate impact on employees' contextual performance, having a 31 percent influence on workers who are white and work in the service sector ($P=0.000$). The study comes to the conclusion that despite perceived organizational support had a minor positive impact on contextual performance. According to the study, the state of employee performance is significantly influenced by perceptions of the support provided to organizations. These perceptions are growing along with cultural stakes of perception toward the provision of contextual performance in the employees among the organizations.

b) Hypothesis 2 (H2): Perceived organizational support significantly and favorably affects workers' work engagement.

Employees in Turkey's white-collar servant sector had a 27.4% greater likelihood of being engaged at work ($P=0.000$), demonstrating that the impact of perceived organizational support on employee engagement is minimal. The study comes to the conclusion that employee engagement at work is significantly influenced by perceptions of organizational support. The study comes to the conclusion that one of the most important factors in achieving work engagement is the perception of organizational support. The study's findings show that perceived organizational support can sustain levels and stakes of employee engagement. The support's values are significant in pursuing and receiving levels of employee engagement, and mechanisms are developed to support efficiency and effectiveness of the businesses to achieve effective decision-making.

c) Hypothesis 3 (H3) Analysis demonstrates transformational leadership's moderate impact on the link between employees' contextual performance and their perception of organizational support

According to the findings, transformational leadership significantly predicted how well employees perceived their organization's support and performed in their current context ($P = 0.000$, $R = .361$). According to the study's findings, there is a weak correlation between perceived organizational support and contextual performance and transformation leadership. The study's findings indicate that transformation is typically induced in moderate forms because transformation leadership influences the relationship between perceived organization support and contextual performance of the personnel. The organization is concentrating its efforts on creating cultural values that are essential to achieving changed employee performance. It is essential to maintain that transformational leadership can support the context of the workforce, which is crucial for increasing awareness and building a focus on the organization. The importance of leadership and transformed leadership is typically understood to motivate leaders to adopt transformational practices crucial to achieving improved contextual performance among people in businesses.

d) Hypothesis 4 (H4) Employees' perceptions of organizational support and their level of work engagement (WE) were moderately analyzed in connection to transformational leadership.

According to the results, transformational leadership was a highly significant predictor of employees' perceived organizational support and work engagement ($P = 0.000$). According to the study's findings, transformation leadership considerably moderates the association between employees' perceived organizational support and job engagement. According to the study's findings, transformation leadership is most suited to fostering a connection between white employees' perceptions of organizational success and their level of work engagement in Turkey's service sector. The study makes the claim that the value leadership and cultural values of the organizations are important in fostering the performance stakes and values required in the organizations. It also claims that these values and leadership practices are an important avenue in assessing the state of the workforce and communities required to create the engagement stakes and values systems for the organizations.

B. Limitations and Recommendations

The study's first limitation is that it only pertained to the majority of Turkish workers who were of the white race. This may limit the study's potential to collect data from rural areas rather than urban ones. Further analysis of potential moderators of the interactions between the variables is required by future researchers in light of transformative leadership. Studies of this kind need to be expanded to include non-colored public service and private sector employees. It is important to remember that different leadership systems must be used in organizations to develop and manage as a means of increasing the effectiveness of the supposed support systems, there is a need for the development of support systems, to improve leadership programs that are even more needed in producing a work plan between people in communities needed to establish people and responsibility.

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